

"Ammonius, On the Creation of the World" by Zacharias Scholasticus

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christian monasticism, Christianity, Syriac Text, Religious Group, Byzantine, Text, Hagiography, Byzantine text

"Ammonius, on the eternity of the world" is a dialogue written by Zacharias Scholasticus (or rhetor, or Zacharias bishop of Mytilene), a native of Gaza who lived between c. 465-536, was a fierce partisan of Monophysitism but ended up as an Orthodox bishop of Mytilene. Zacharias's dialogue is important, as it provides a vivid and detailed picture of the student environment in 5th century Alexandria, its philosophical schools and the lively debate between pagans and Christians during that period. Nevertheless, the date that Zacharias composed his dialogue remains unknown, since we lack both internal and external testimonies that can provide us with some relatively reliable indications in this regard. It seems, however, that the dialogue "Ammonius" is a work of its author's maturity: here, Zacharias does not deviate from official Orthodoxy, does not indulge in doctrinal compromises, nor does he allow himself to be misled by heretical tendencies. All this suggests that the dialogue was written after Zacharias had definitively renounced the monophysitism of his youth. "Ammonius" in fact records the conversation between two persons identified as "A" and "B". It begins with a short prologue, the only narrative part written in the first person, where the narrator is identified speaker "A". While the dialogue between "A" and "B" is not framed by an audience or a third person, the lectures with Ammonius and the iatrosophist Gessius take place in front of an audience, whose reactions are meticulously recorded. The dialogue opens with the unexpected meeting of a Christian (speaker "A", evidently Zacharias himself) and a disciple of the philosopher Ammonius (speaker "B", presumably a Christian, who is said to be leaning towards paganism) in Beirut, where the latter has moved from Alexandria to study law. Speaker "A" takes the opportunity of the meeting to ask about the philosopher Ammonius, but his mocking and accusatory tone prompts "B" to question his interlocutor's hostility towards the philosopher. This prompts speaker "A" to refer to four discourses: three with the philosopher Ammonius himself in Alexandria and one, in the same city, with the iatrosophist Gessius. The first discourse between the Christian and Ammonius is intense and soon the conversation shifts and takes on more of a confrontation between Christianity and pagan philosophical ideas. Both interlocutors refer to authoritative authors of their tradition, including Plato and Porphyry, while Christian's extensive argumentation ends with the Apostle Paul and Solomon. Ammonius acknowledges the Christian's victory at certain points, and the narrative closes by recording the audience's preference for Christian positions. The second discourse takes place the next day and is instigated by Gessius, one of Ammonius's best students. The scenery however is different: the discussion is taking place at the Museum of Alexandria, "where poets, orators, and grammarians are wont to display their skill." Plato is often cited and considered authoritative by both parties. The Christian speaker, who is frequently using passages from "Timaeus" to foster his arguments, argues that the Holy Scripture, St. Basil the Great, the Stoics, and Plato himself agree that the universe will perish. Although Gessius initially appears bewildered and dazzled by the Christian arguments, as the conversation progresses, he recognizes their authority, even if there is no clear admission on his part. The third discourse takes place during Ammonius's lecture on Aristotelian ethics. The debate is intense. Ammonius is struck by the Christian arguments. The final discourse between the Christian and Ammonius, significantly shorter than the previous ones, is motivated by the philosopher, who questions the Christian teaching about the Holy Trinity. Ammonius, however, is soon convinced by the response he receives, causing a joyful reaction to the audience. He then blushes, falls silent and avoids any further conversation. After the four discourses, the discussion between "A" and "B" continues, as the latter is still unconvinced. Here, speaker "A" develops an extensive argument using

passages from the Scriptures, from the works of Clement of Alexandria, St. Basil the Great, and St. Gregory of Nazianzus. The dialogue ends with "B's" acceptance of Christian doctrine, as presented by "A", who then utters a prayer.

Date Range: 490 CE - 520 CE

Region: Alexandria in Egypt

Region tags: Alexandria, Byzantium, Egypt, Eastern Mediterranean

Alexandria

Status of Readership:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Maria Minniti Colonna, Zacaria Scolastico, "Ammonio." Introduzione, testo critico, traduzione, commentario, Napoli 1973.
- Source 2: Aeneas of Gaza "Theophrastus." Translated by John Dillon and Donald Russell with Zacharias of Mytilene "Ammonius." Translated by Sebastian Gertz, (Ancient Commentators of Aristotle, επιμ. Richard Sorabji), Bloomsbury Academic: London 2012.
- Source 3: Lampros Alexopoulos, "Ζαχαρίας Σχολαστικός "Ἀμμώνιος ἢ περὶ δημιουργίας κόσμου", Thessaloniki, 2023

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://syriaca.org/person/58>
- Source 1 Description: Zechariah Rhetor, The Syriac Biographical Dictionary

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

–Other textile: parchment

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Zacharias only mentions the audience that participated at the classes of Ammonius and Gessius. Their number, however, is not cited precisely.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: The so-called called "Philoponoi" (Lovers of toil or Diligent), was a group of Alexandrian Monophysitic lay Christians active in debating pagan professors of philosophy. The "Philoponoi" cared for the sick and the poor, undertook various church duties and monitored the activities of pagan professors for sacrifices or relative cult practices. This group tried to converse into Christianity all the pagan students that participated at the classes of pagan philosophers and rhetors in Alexandria.

Reference: Trombly, Frank. *Hellenic Religion and Christianization: C. 370-529*. Vol. 2. Boston, Leiden: Brill, 2001.

Reference: Haas, Christopher. *Alexandria in Late Antiquity: Topography and Social Conflict*. Baltimore:

Johns Hopkins University Press, 1997.

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: "Ammonius" is the only text written by Zacharias that survived in Greek language. All of his other works were destroyed (they survive only in Syriac translation) due to the fact that Zacharias was a member of the Monophysite party.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: Quite vaguely, the text may be considered as a part of the effort made by the main figures of the school of Gaza to refute neoplatonic doctrines on the eternity of the world. It may also be seen as a precursor so to speak, of John Philoponus' detailed refutation posited in this latter's "De Aeternitate Mundi".

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text includes sophisticated philosophical terms.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: The so-called food chain argument

Notes: A lively debate regarding the resurrection of the [dead] bodies is cited in Zacharias's dialogue is of particular interest, as it is an intellectual challenge posed by the pagans to the Christians, almost four centuries before Zacharias and his dialogue. We find this argument as early as the second century AD in Athenagoras of Athens (*De resurrectione*), in Tatian (2nd century AD), in Tertullian (2nd -3d c. AD), later in St. Augustine, in Cyril of Jerusalem and Gregory of Nyssa (both 4th c. AD)

Reference: Sorabji, Richard . *Self. Ancient and Modern Insights About Individuality, Life, and Death*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2006.

Reference: Harnack, Adolf. *Porphyrius, "gegen Die Christen" 15 Bücher. Zeugnisse, Fragmente Und Referate*. Berlin: Verlag de Königlich Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1916.

Reference: Alexopoulos, Lampros. "Η Φυσιολογία Τοῦ Πεπτικοῦ Συστήματος Στὴν Ἐπιχειρηματολογία Τοῦ Ἀπολογητῆ Ἀθηναγόρα Ὑπὲρ Τῆς Ἀναστάσεως Τῶν Σωμάτων", 2016*Theologia* 87.4.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias refers to Gessius, who buried according to the pagan ritual customs, one of his friends.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, it should be noted that Zacharias refers, sadly quite vaguely and in passing, to the ontological hierarchy of reality. The idea of this ontological chain was first systematized by Plotinus, although its basic concepts derive from Plato's Idea of the Good, bound by the principle of

completeness to produce every possible Idea and temporal existence, and Aristotle's "Scala Naturae", who wanted to organize all things in the natural world in a continuum from "lower" to "higher" forms of matter. Plotinus, in his turn, integrated Platonic and Aristotelian philosophy by developing a hierarchical system of transcendental realities (substances) as follows: the One, which constitutes the ultimate reality and source of emanation of beings; the Mind, which is the Divine Mind, the Platonic archetypes and the cosmic Soul, the principle behind the universe, which moves everything, the universal equivalent of the individual mind or soul. Subsequent Neoplatonic philosophers, such as Iamblichus and Proclus, enriched Plotinus's hierarchical system by adding more and more substances and by replacing the mystical immediacy of the One with a series of progressively transcendent layers.

Reference: Lovejoy, Arthur . *The Great Chain of Being. A Study of the History of an Idea.* Cambridge MA : Harvard University Press, 1964.

Reference: Granger, Herbert . "The Scala Naturae and the Continuity of Kinds", 1985.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/4182226>Phronesis 30,2.

Reference: Granger, Herbert . "Aristotle and the Finitude of Natural Kinds", 1987.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/3750932>Philosophy Vol. 62, No. 242.

Reference: Verrycken, Koenraad. "La Métaphysique D' ammonius Chez Zacharie De Mytilène" 85 (2001).
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/44410150>Revue des Sciences philosophiques et théologiques.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
– No

↳ At specified time in future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– Yes

↳ At some other time [specify]
– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world
– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: The resurrection from the dead.

Notes: Zacharias discusses quite extensively the theological "problem" of the resurrection of the dead and the final restoration of mankind.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Field doesn't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: We learn, however, that the author and his close friends, the so-called Philoponoi, spent much time in the local Christian temples, where they could discuss on matters of faith, study the works of the Church Fathers and provide, also, assistance to the local Church authorities.

Reference: Petrides, Sophrone. "Spoudaei Et Philopones", 1904 *Échos d' Orient* 7:49 .

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A federation or league

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A federation or league

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Zacharias mentions the famous Neoplatonic school of Alexandria, where Ammonius, son of Hermias, taught philosophy. Ammonius began his career as a teacher at the school of Horapollon, which functioned as a hub of "Greek" pagan learning, religion, and culture within a Christian Alexandria. He was unlucky, however, because the rebellion of Illus, a pagan official of the Byzantine state, deeply affected the teaching of philosophy in Alexandria. Ammonius seems to have come to an agreement with the Christian Patriarch of Alexandria, that allowed him to the unhindered continuation of Neoplatonic studies in Alexandria. Thus, Ammonius is said to have agreed: (a) to continue the Alexandrian Neoplatonic tradition by eliminating "symbolic and theological" interpretation, (b) to deliver lectures only on Aristotle, not Plato, and not to mention in his teaching the Aristotelian doctrine on the eternity and the divine nature of the world, (c) to betray his colleagues by revealing the locations

where these latter were hiding in order to protect his position as a professor.

Reference: Sorabji, Richard . "Introduction to the Second Edition. New Findings on Philoponus, Part I: The Classrooms Excavated". London: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010.

Reference: Szabat, Elzbieta . "Teachers in the Eastern Roman Empire (fifth to Seventh Century): A Historical Study and Prosopography". Warsaw: Journal of Juristic Papyrology supp. 8, 2007.

Reference: Watts, Edward. "Student Travel to Intellectual Centers: What Was the Attraction?". Aldershot: Routledge, 2004.

Reference: Vedeshkin, Mikhail. "Bribe and Punishment: To the Question of Persistence of Pagan Cults in Late Antiquity" 12 (2018). <https://doi.org/DOI:10.21267/AQUILO.2018.12.10429Schole> .

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the fact that Zacharias provides us with invaluable information on the way that philosophy was taught in Alexandria during the 5th century, he also refers to the relationship between teachers and students. He mentions, for example, that Christian teachers gathered their students in their homes every Friday, while there are also references to the close relationships between pagan teachers and their students.

Reference: Watts, Edward. *Riot in Alexandria: Tradition and Group Dynamics in Late Antique Pagan and Christian Communities*. Oakland: California University Press, 2010.

Reference: Chuvin, Pierre. *Chronique Des Derniers Païens. La Disparition Du Paganisme Dans L'empire Romain, Du Règne De Constantin À Celui De Justinien*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1990.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: Zacharias however provides a detailed and vivid description of the Church of Anastasia in Beirut, which was built by Eustathius of Antioch.

Reference: Jones Hall, Linda . *Roman Berytus. Beirut in Late Antiquity*. London: Routledge, 2004.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Antioch, Syria

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Institutum Patristicum Augustinianum, 1996.

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Reference: No, Granger, Herbert. "Aristotle and the Finitude of Natural Kinds", 1987. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3750932>Philosophy Vol. 62, No. 242.

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